

Proposed Framework To Evaluate The Ability Of Digital Measures To Track Early Stage Parkinson's Disease Progression

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Introduction

Objectives. To introduce a technical framework for evaluating digital measures for their ability to track Parkinson's disease (PD) progression and to apply the framework to digital measures of physical activity collected via wrist-worn sensors.

Background. Mobility and physical activity are meaningful aspects of health for people with PD. Mobility impairments represent one of the most important and impactful symptom domains in the disease. PD progression can be often tracked by changes in mobility and declines in physical activity.¹⁻³

Wearable sensors enable remote, objective, and continuous monitoring of physical activity in people with PD.^{4,5} However, there is little consensus on how to validate digital measures⁶ for monitoring disease progression. This is especially relevant in early-stage PD, where traditional gold-standard clinical instruments (e.g., movement disorder society-sponsored unified PD rating scale [MDS-UPDRS]) may not be sensitive enough to detect disease progression in the initial years following diagnosis and thus not be optimal as endpoints for drug trials with people with early-stage PD.

Methods

Evaluation Framework. A measure can track early-stage PD progression if:

- In people with PD, the measure value changes over time with statistical significance, and the direction of change aligns with clinical expectations of disease progression (e.g., lower physical activity with progression).
- The measure shows good test-retest reliability (e.g., intraclass correlation coefficient [ICC] of two consecutive monthly aggregated measures >0.75).
- People with PD have significantly larger measure changes compared to demographically matched people without PD.

Study cohort. Verily Study Watch (VSW)-derived walking and non-walking measures (see below) were evaluated using data from the Personalized Parkinson Project (PPP). Two years of free-living sensor data was collected from 224 participants who had less than 4 years of PD diagnosis at enrollment via VSW. The study includes 514 participants where a subset (N=212) is currently held out as a test set.

Figure. Verily Study Watch (VSW)⁸

⁸CAUTION: Investigational device. Limited by Federal (or United States) law to investigational use.

Table. Demographic and clinical characteristics of the study cohort N=224

Mean age, yrs (SD)	61.5 (8.7)
Sex, n (%)	Male 137 (61.2) Female 87 (38.8)
Time from 1st symptom onset, yrs (SD)	2.1 (1.1)
Mean Hoehn and Yahr score (SD)	2.0 (0.5)
Mean MDS-UPDRS total scores (SD)	Part I 14.9 (7.6) Part II 8.4 (5.9) Part III 33.5 (12.9) Part IV 2.9 (3.2)
Mean PDQ-39 (SD)	32.1 (18.9)
Mean Schwab and England ADL (SD)	90.6 (9.0)

ADL= Activities of daily living; MDS-UPDRS = Movement disorder society-sponsored unified Parkinson's disease rating scale; PDQ-39 = Parkinson's disease questionnaire - 39; SD = Standard deviation

Digital Measures. Following daily measures of walking and non-walking behavior from the VSW were used in this study.⁷⁻¹⁰

Category	Measure Name	Descriptions
Walking quantity	Step count	Summed number of steps per day
	Ambulatory minutes	Summed total minutes of walking per day
Walking bouts	Bout duration (mean, std, 95%)	Duration of daily walking bouts (≥30 seconds)
	Number of bouts (total, short, long)	Number of daily walking bouts (≥30 seconds)
	Fraction of (long, short) bouts	Fraction of (long, short) bouts out of total daily walking bouts
Walking cadence	Peak cadence (15, 30, 60 minutes)	Average of the highest 10-sec cadence epochs of the day (for 15, 30, 60 minutes, not necessarily contiguous)
	Cadence (std, 75%, 95%)	Number of steps per second for the day
	Cadence within bouts (std, 75%, 95%)	Number of steps per second during walking bouts (≥ 2 minutes)
Non-walking quantity	Non-walking minutes	Summed total minutes of NWB (excluding sleep time) per day
Non-walking bouts (NWB)	NWB duration (mean, std, 95%)	Duration of daily NWB
	Number of NWB (total, short, long)	Number of NWB per day
	Fraction of (long, short) NWB	Fraction of NWB greater than ≥ X minutes out of total non-walking minutes per day (X=1, 2, 5, 15)
NWB pattern	NWB Gini Index	Measure of the daily distribution of short NWB vs. long NWB
	Time to 80% total daily bout duration	Time required to reach 80% of total daily non-walking minutes

Results

Out of 57 VSW-based digital measures of walking and non-walking behavior, 42 candidate single measures were initially selected based on the first two criteria in the evaluation framework (the third criterion was not addressed due to lack of a non-PD cohort for this study dataset), indicating they can capture longitudinal change, and have good test-retest reliability.

- [Evaluation criterion 1] 46 measures passed mixed model analysis (false discovery rate [FDR] corrected p-value <= 0.05)
- [Evaluation criterion 2] 49 measures passed test-retest analysis (lower bound of 95% confidence interval [CI] of ICC > 0.75)

Effect Size

(Absolute Cohen's d)

Baseline vs Year 1

Context: Effect Size of Conventional Clinical Measures (from the same dataset)

Measure	Absolute Cohen's d	
	Baseline vs Year 2	Year 1
MDS-UPDRS Part 3 gait	0.136	0.072
MDS-UPDRS Part 3 - tremor	0.452	0.293
MDS-UPDRS Part 3 - facial expression/speech/tremor ¹¹	0.421	0.269
MDS-UPDRS Part 2 + 3 - tremor	0.460	0.306
PDQ-39 mobility	0.233	0.150
Schwab & England ADL	0.470	0.249
MDS-UPDRS Part 3 total	0.359	0.236
MDS-UPDRS Part 2 total	0.398	0.247
MDS-UPDRS Part 2+3 total	0.372	0.249
MDS-UPDRS Part 1+2+3 total	0.358	0.239

ADL= Activities of Daily Living; MDS-UPDRS=Movement Disorder Society-sponsored Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale; PDQ-39=Parkinson's Disease Questionnaire - 39

Using clinical benchmarks for context (*):

- Over 2 years, 22 measures (8 walking, 14 non-walking) outperformed clinical benchmarks, with absolute Cohen's d values ranging 0.02-0.77.
- Over 1 year, 24 measures (9 walking, 15 non-walking) outperformed clinical benchmarks, with absolute Cohen's d values ranging 0-0.47

* Clinical benchmark: Cohen's d values from traditional clinical measures commonly used as primary / secondary endpoints in PD trials. (Eg, Schwab and England ADL, various MDS-UPDRS score combinations, obtained in the study dataset)

Common primary/secondary PD trial endpoints

Month-to-month Test-retest Reliability (ICC)

This analysis demonstrates the stability of these measures to be used longitudinally in clinical studies, where data can be collected passively and aggregated monthly.

- Overall good-to-excellent month-to-month test-retest reliability (> 0.75 ICC) for all measures
- Number of short walking bouts, peak cadence walking measures and number of non-walking bouts are the most reliable measures (~0.9 ICC)

Summary of Representative Measures

Category	Measure	Change (%)		Est. monthly increment (95% CI)	Abs. Cohen's d		
		At yr 1	At yr 2		Year 1	Year 2	
Non-walking quantity	Non-walking minutes	10.0 (0.9)	20.1 (1.6)	0.837 (0.290, 1.384)	0.12	0.18	
	NWB	Mean non-walking bout duration, min	4.99 (17.7)	9.97 (39.3)	24.928 (17.771, 32.086)	0.47	0.64
NWB Pattern	Walking quantity	Number of all non-walking bouts	-4.1 (-8.9)	-8.2 (-17.5)	-0.342 (-0.435, -0.249)	0.4	0.69
		Number of non-walking bouts (≥ 15min)	-0.6 (-4.4)	-1.2 (-11.9)	-0.049 (-0.054, -0.043)	0.31	0.77
		95 % of non-walking bout duration, min	14.96 (13.9)	29.92 (32.1)	74.808 (54.098, 95.518)	0.45	0.72
		Time to 80% of total non-walking bout duration	15.69 (12.4)	31.37 (29.1)	78.423 (50.645, 106.202)	0.37	0.69
Walking quantity	Step count	-604.7 (-7.3)	-1209.4 (-11.4)	-50.39 (-64.973, -35.813)	0.34	0.51	
	Ambulatory minutes	-5.7 (-8.5)	-11.4 (-13.7)	-0.475 (-0.602, -0.348)	0.34	0.49	
Walking bouts	Number of walking bouts	-4.0 (-9.2)	-8.1 (-18.2)	-0.337 (-0.430, -0.243)	0.39	0.67	
Walking cadence	Peak 15-min cadence, steps/sec	-0.023 (-1.4)	-0.045 (-2.4)	-0.002 (-0.003, -0.001)	0.32	0.48	

CI=confidence interval; NWB=non-walking bouts

Figure. Analysis of the change for one of the measures average NWB, as example.

Summary and Next Steps

- Using a developmental dataset obtained from a cohort of individuals with early-stage PD, we selected 42 measures of walking and non-walking behavior based on the initial two criteria of the proposed evaluation framework.
- These 42 measures have 2-year Cohen's d values ranging 0.02-0.77, with good-to-excellent test-retest reliability. Of them, 22 measures showed Cohen's d values greater than traditional clinical measures commonly used as primary or secondary endpoints in PD interventional trials, such as MDS-UPDRS and Schwab and England ADL.
- According to the proposed framework, our results suggest that these measures of walking and non-walking behaviors are reliable and sensitive to capture physical activity changes in people with early-stage PD.
 - Measures detect physical activity decline over 1 or 2 years.
 - Specifically, the increase in duration of total non-walking periods and individual NWB, together with the decrease in number of NWB, could suggest a clustering of non-walking periods as PD progresses.
- Further research is needed to compare these measures in people with and without PD, in order to meet all the framework criteria and confirm that the detected changes are due to disease progression.

Abbreviations

- ADL= Activities of daily living
- CI = Confidence interval
- FDR = False discovery rate
- ICC = Intraclass correlation coefficient
- MDS-UPDRS = Movement disorder society-sponsored unified Parkinson's disease rating scale
- NWB = Non-walking bout
- PD = Parkinson's disease
- PDQ-39 = Parkinson's disease questionnaire - 39
- PPP = Personalized Parkinson project
- SD = Standard deviation
- VSW = Verily study watch

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Disclosures

KCH, CC, SS, SL, NK, ER, RK report employment and equity ownership in Verily Life Sciences.

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